

Social Media Research and Its Effect on Our Society

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III. METHODOLOGY

At first select the topic base on objectives. A vast literature review has been done to determine the analytical output. A questioner is prepared for field survey data collection. SPSS data output has been shown the required results.

IV. SAMPLE SIZE DETERMINATION

Total numbers of students have been used for the determination of sample size. The initial sample size was determined by the following formula [1]:

$$n = \frac{z^2 pq}{d^2}$$

where, Z is the normal variety and which has 1.65 for 90% confidence interval; p is the target proportion. In this case, we have assumed p= 0.5; p+q =1, therefore q=0.5; and d is the desired error which is 0.1.

The initial sample size is therefore:

$$n_0 = \frac{(1.65)^2 \times 0.5 \times 0.5}{(0.1)} = 68.0625$$

These sample size was adjusted by using the following formula:

$$n = \frac{n_0}{1 + \frac{n_0}{N}} = 67.87 \cong 68$$

where n is requiring sample size and N is Total numbers of students is about 32371(apex.). The sample size has been distributed among the three universities named Govt. Bangla College, America Bangladesh University and Pangsha University College in Dhaka city.

V. ANALYSIS

A. Social Media Choice

The oldest and most powerful form of mass media is the word, both written and spoken; from catholic priests to traveling storytellers, the word has held credibility [5]. A new platform, social media, has taken the power of the word to new levels, transforming companies, society communication. Platforms such as Twitter and Facebook are conduits for dialogues between many to many, held in a very visible format. This new format is altering the methods of advertising, merging both the advertiser and the advertised. If a company hopes to succeed in this new generation of technology they must embrace social media. Social networking sites are small virtual villages. Different people use different communication

Abstract—Social media refers to the means of interactions among people in which they create share, exchange and comment contents among themselves in virtual communities and networks. Social media or "social networking" has almost become part of our daily lives and being tossed around over the past few years. It is like any other media such as newspaper, radio and television but it is far more than just about sharing information and ideas. Social networking tools like Twitter, Facebook, Flickr and Blogs have facilitated creation and exchange of ideas so quickly and widely than the conventional media. This paper shows the choices, communication, feeling comfort, time saving and effects of social media among the people.

Keywords—Media, Choice, Effect.

I. INTRODUCTION

IN the past five years, social media websites have become ubiquitous, giving young people a new way to interact with each other and communicate with the world. This new form of communication depends on user created content, not mass produced messages coming from large media companies. But as with other media before it, social media's rise to prominence has experienced some very serious growing pains. Companies like Facebook, MySpace, and Twitter have struggled to balance an inviting interactive environment with the ultimate pursuit of profit. This issue of the paper aims to explore some of the issues related to social media, and a generation fully engaged in this interactive world. The main focus is popular social media sites such as Facebook, MySpace, Twitter, Wikipedia, YouTube, and LinkedIn, but other social networking sites are explored as well. In this paper there 67 sample size has been distributed among the three universities named Govt. Bangla college, America Bangladesh University and Pangsha university college in Dhaka city. It offered suggestions, guidance, communication media choice, influences factors, some opinion about social media choice.

A. Objective

The aim is to discuss about the interactive environment of social media, media choice and effects.

II. STUDY AREA

67 sample sizes have been distributed among the three universities named Govt. Bangla College, America Bangladesh University and Pangsha University College in Dhaka City.

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sites like Social networking sites (face book, twitter, MSN, Skype, Google talk), Voice calling (telephone, cell phone and intercom), through writing (email, letter and fax), Face to face communication (meeting). A figure has been show that most of the people use now face book, twitter, MSN, Skype, Google talk.

Fig. 1 Communication media choice

B. Communication Media Using Schedule

Communication is the essential element that creates and maintains relationships. In this day and age; communication technology has developed to become both simple and fast. For example, we no longer need to look up old classmates in phone directories anymore in order to find out what they've been doing. Instead, we use social media networks such as Facebook and MySpace in order to keep ourselves updated on our family and friends' lives no matter where they are in the world. According to statistics, Facebook has more than 400 million active users, and about 50% of them log on to Facebook at any given day (Fig. 2). People also spend more than 55 minutes on Facebook using daily.

Fig. 2 Communication media using schedule

Again, most of the people use at a highest percentage cell

phone daily, YouTube use weekly and email monthly (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3 Communication media using schedule compares

C. Communication Media Preferences

Our questionnaires' survey data analysis show that about 15% people highly like communication media and about 60% people like media because of its beefiness (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4 Communication media preferences

D. Social Media Feeling Comfort and Time Saving

Our questionnaires' survey data analysis show that about 48% people are feeling comfort on Social networking sites (Facebook, twitter, MSN, Skype, Google talk) and about 53% people thinking Voice calling (telephone, cell phone and intercom) is perfect for time as well as money saving media (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5 Social media feeling comfort and time saving

E. Social Media Secureness and Flexibility

Survey data analysis shows that about more than 50% people are feeling secure in face to face communication and more than 40% people flexible on voice calling media.

Fig. 6 Social media secureness and flexibility

F. Social Media in Our Modern Civilization

Social media has become this significant part of our modern civilization. It is a defining trait of how integrated our social interactions have become. We credit this achievement to the developments that have made in technology to ingenuity of the

visionaries among us, who, in creating social networking platforms, have helped write some of the present occurrences being experienced in the world today.

Fig. 7 Facebook, Twitter, and Google+ - A different world of social networking

With Facebook, Twitter, Google+ and other social networks we have become much aware of the world we are living in and this is one of the changes being talked about. Social Networking giants like Facebook, Twitter, and Google+ have contributed to create a whole new world where free to express our opinion and share it with friends and peers [3]. This world of social media gives scope to everyone to express and share ideas, thoughts and feelings, who want to be the part of it. Within the past ten years, social media such as Twitter, Facebook, MySpace, YouTube, Flickr, and others have grown at a tremendous rate, enlisting an astronomical number of users. Social media have inevitably become an integral part of the contemporary classroom, of advertising and public relations industries, of political campaigning, and of numerous other aspects of our daily existence [4]. All chapters constitute original research while using varied research methodologies for analyzing and presenting information about social media. Social Media: Usage and Impact is a tremendous source for educators, practitioners (such as those in advertising, P.R., and media industries), and librarians, among others. This collection is an essential resource for any media technology course. With the rapid proliferation and adoption of social media, it is a juggernaut that must be addressed in the higher education curriculum and research [5].

VI. FINDINGS

A. The Effects of Social Media on Teenagers

Children today are as technologically connected as anyone on the planet has ever been. They have access to social media like Facebook, Integral and Twitter and they can be able to chat in real time with their friends who are a thousand miles away. Various reports suggest that about eighty-three percent of American youth use their phones for email, mobile internet and texting. The report further states that these American teens send and receive text messages 144 times a day [2]. If the teens are not texting, they are usually on social networking sites like Facebook and Twitter where they chat, share photos

and video and participate in gaming. The negative effects of being this “plugged in” are beginning to take enormous effect on kids. Because social interaction comes overwhelmingly online rather than face to face, American youth are showing severe lack of social skills. They are often more comfortable with technology than they are with talking to people. They have not learned the proper communication and conversation skills, how to deal with interpersonal situations and how to date and get to know other people behind the screen. Researchers have found that the middle-school, high school and college students who used Facebook at least once during a 15 minute period get lower grades overall [3].

B. Reasons for Negative Effects of Media on Teens

Many teens usually spend sleepless nights on social media without the knowledge of their parents. The disruption of sleep has had adverse effects on the teens. It has led to cases of insomnia, mood swings, attention deficits at school and increased obesity just to mention a few. These are some of the serious negative effects of social media on teenagers and issues that are arising with kids often addicted to Facebook. With such overwhelming evidence of the negative effects of social media on our children, why then, are many parents not taking more action to protect their children?

There perhaps are three major reasons:

- 1) Parents are unaware of the issues involved in the online connections. While kids are plugged in to social media, only about 40% of parents are involved themselves [4]. Parents may not be aware of their children’s “pages” and don’t fully understand privacy policies and they don’t realize what kinds of public postings are taking place, involving their children.
- 2) Parents don’t want to interfere in their children’s social lives. Most parents want their children to be popular, accepted and enjoy a happy social life. Parents sometimes concern themselves with children’s “rights” – their right to privacy and their right to interact in today’s popular forums [5]. Parents want to allow their children to be as connected as the other kids they associate with, and so they tell themselves that everything is ok.
- 3) Parents are afraid to take a stand. Many of “modern” parents are becoming apathetic to the real dangers that too much social media can present to their children [4]. They don’t want to push their teens away and so they allow their participation in social media to go unchecked rather than make a “big deal” out of it [2].

The problems this new online society creates are not going away and will continue to grow. Parents must get off the sidelines and get involved! Parents have the responsibility to protect their children and be aware of what is going on in the online world. Investigate and help your child adjust privacy settings. Be aware of who can see what they post, and what is being posted about them. Talk with them about online safety. Make sure your teens have plenty of offline time as well. Restrict the times and frequency of online interaction.

Place all phones in the docking station at night where they are required to stay until everyone leaves for work and school

in the morning. Consider allowing siblings to share a phone they can “check out” from mom or dad.

Create family-determined “unplugged” hours when children can participate in other activities such as outdoor games, reading, talking, playing together etc. [3].

Social media has a tremendous effect on us today, but with parental participation and kids’ cooperation, the effects can be positive for everyone.

VII. CONCLUSION

A. Positives Effects

1. Meeting people you may not have met outside the social media forums
2. Sharing ideas beyond the geographical boundaries-like am doing now.
3. Reducing travelling costs, costs of buying books and other references especially if you need a page or two in the whole book and other costs
4. Expansion of democratic space. With some governments imposing serious mass media ban, social media can offer some outlet
5. You can persuade your pals to maintain peace in your society through the social media
6. If you combine social media and other media, you can reach more people for purposes of business, education, health etc.

B. Negatives Effects

Social media can be abused by its users too. It’s not fair for people to discuss anyone on social media platforms without consent. Then there is personification [5]. You may not know whether the image i use is my real one this may encourage the society to be falsely. Social ties like family ones can also weaken as people spend more time connecting to new people. As long as the basic human need to connect is met online, offline friends may not be regarded.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

At first all praises belong to Almighty Allah then we express our profound gratitude and Indebtedness to our friends and classmates Mohd. Mostakim and Al-kauser, students of Department of Urban and Regional Planning (URP), Chittagong University of Engineering and Technology for their cordial encouragement, constant guidance, inspiration and valuable suggestion to prepare this paper.

REFERENCES

- [1] Hasan, MR (2010), ‘land use and land value in urban fringe area of khulna, bangladesh’, MURP thesis, Bangladesh University of Engineering and Technology, Dhaka, Bangladesh
- [2] Housley, Sharon. “RSS Feeds and Copyright Law.” World Law Direct. 3 May 2010. Web.http://www.worldlawdirect.com/article/ 3331/rss-feeds-copyright-law.html
- [3] J. J. Burns. And D. R. Anderson. “Attentional Inertia and Recognition Memory in Adult Television Viewing,” *Communication Research* 20 (1993): 777–99.
- [4] Matyszczyk, Chris. "Facebook Entry Gets Office Worker Fired." Technically Incorrect 26 Feb. 2009: n. pag. Web. 17 May 2013. <http://news.cnet.com/ 8301-17852_3-10172931-71.html>.

- [5] R. D. Hess and L. J. McGarvey, "School-Relevant Effects of Educational Uses of Microcomputers in Kindergarten Classrooms and Homes," *Journal of Educational Computing Research* 3 (1987): 269–87.